

IRONIC STYLE IN THE TRANSLATION PROCESS AND ITS REFLECTION

Tashpulatova Mukambar Axmetovna

Associate professor of the “Foreign Languages” Department at Tashkent State Transport University

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Abstract. *This article aims to study the expression of ironic style in the translation process and its examination from the perspective of linguistics, particularly stylistic pragmatics. The linguopragmatic features of irony, its semantic complexity, and its role in intercultural communication are illuminated. Issues of correct interpretation of ironic units in translator activity and their reflection in appropriate expressions in the target language are discussed. The article analyzes various stylistic-functional aspects of irony based on the works of Russian and English translation theorists.*

Keywords: *Ironic style, translation theory, stylistic pragmatics, linguopragmatics, contextual compatibility, intercultural communication, hidden meaning.*

Introduction. In contemporary research directions of translatology, stylistic pragmatics stands out as an important methodological foundation. This approach ensures high scientific precision, particularly in analyzing ironic style. Ironic content presents meaning in a multi-layered manner in the communication process through its semantic and pragmatic duality. The translator must be able to identify such ambiguous expressions and express them in a semantically consistent and stylistically appropriate form. This requires the organic interconnection of analysis, interpretation, and conversion stages in the translation process. The expression of irony occurs not only at the textual level but also at the discursive level. In this case, hidden communication emerges between the author and the reader. The translator functions as a mediating facilitator who can capture this hidden communication. Among stylistic devices, the linguopragmatic features of irony distinguish it from other expressive methods. One of the important tasks for the translator is to identify these features, analyze them, and create unique stylistic dynamics in the new linguistic environment.

Irony sometimes possesses extremely social or political connotations. In this case, it is appropriate to use the method of functional adaptation rather than direct translation. In functional adaptation, the translator attempts to find equivalents that correspond to the system of social and cultural codes in the Uzbek language. In this approach, the translator’s level of social consciousness and cultural perceptual activity plays an important role. To understand ironic content, linguistic competence alone is insufficient; cognitive and contextual understanding are also necessary.

Literature Review: The works of scholars such as L.I.Boldina, A.A.Gornostayeva, I.V.Illarionova, and N.A.Maslennikova on the reflection of irony in translation have been thoroughly studied. Boldina interprets irony not as an aesthetic device but as an evaluative and communicative strategy, revealing its important aspects in translation. Gornostayeva analyzes the national-cultural connotations of irony in the English language, emphasizing the importance of decoding these signals in translation. Illarionova's research reveals the differences between ironic expressions in British and American English, while Maslennikova proposes the linguistic

and contextual interpretation of hidden meanings as a methodological foundation. These approaches serve as the basis for the theoretical views and practical examples presented in the article.

In studying the issue of irony's reflection in translation, L.I. Boldina's scientific research titled "Irony as a Manifestation of Comic Phenomena" serves as an important theoretical foundation. The researcher studies irony not only as an aesthetic-stylistic device but also as a communicative strategy. She pays special attention to the evaluative characteristic, which is one of irony's main functions. Through irony, the subject indirectly expresses attitude toward reality, and this attitude is reflected in a manner contrary to surface expression. Boldina distinguishes irony from pure comedy and analyzes its complex semantic structure enriched with social-cultural connotations. According to her, the successful impact of irony often relies on context and intersubjective knowledge. This approach shows contextual sensitivity and cultural thinking as important factors necessary for correct interpretation of irony in the translation process. When transferring ironic units, the translator is not limited to lexical compatibility but must also functionally preserve this evaluative component in the new language.[1] Boldina's scientific views can serve as a basis for preferring stylistic and communicative compatibility criteria over semantic fidelity in the translation process of irony. From this perspective, her works are considered an important source for developing methodological and practical solutions for studying irony in translation activity.

A.A. Gornostayeva's research titled "Irony as a Component of English Communication Style" is devoted to the formation and functional application of irony in national-cultural context, making a relevant contribution to translation theory in this direction. While studying the place of ironic expression in the communicative system of the English language, the author deeply analyzes its linguocultural features. The research illuminates not only the aesthetic-emotional function of irony but also its social evaluative and speech strategic functions. Gornostayeva notes that English irony often relies on expressing thoughts through indirect content, which manifests in the difference between direct meaning and connotative layers. Correctly conveying this dual semantics and stylistic intention emerges as the most important problem in translation. Ironic style in English transmits social signals through cultural codes, and correctly decoding this signal depends on the translator's intercultural competence.[2] Gornostayeva's research views irony not only as a linguistic category but also as a cultural and communicative phenomenon. This approach shows the necessity of transferring irony to another culture without disrupting contextual consistency in the translation process. Her analyses provide clear scientific evidence for the dialogic nature of irony, the coordination of social relationships through it, and the expression of social positions through this device. On this basis, activating irony in translation requires not only semantic transformation but also complete understanding of communicative intention and selection of appropriate means. Gornostayeva's scientific views serve as an important theoretical foundation for contemporary paradigms regarding intercultural translation of irony.

Illarionova's research titled "Contrastive Analysis of Irony Expression in British and American English Variants" is aimed at determining what semantic and pragmatic features irony manifests in regional language variants. The author analyzes that irony in British English is expressed in more socially distanced, indirect, and subtle forms. Simultaneously, it has been determined that American English gives preference to more open ironic expressions, sometimes enriched with satirical elements. In the research, differences between language variants are thoroughly studied on a contextual basis, and phonetic, lexical, and pragmatic differences in the

linguistic expression forms of irony are demonstrated. Illarionova notes functions such as social evaluation, hidden expression of critical thought, and expression of moral position in both variants. She emphasizes the importance of not only linguistic but also cultural studies knowledge for correct interpretation of this stylistic device in translation.[3] If the translator lacks knowledge about the mentality, moral norms, and social customs of communication participants, the original meaning of irony may be lost or misinterpreted. Illarionova's contrastive analysis creates a foundation for developing methodological approaches necessary for accurate and content-appropriate transfer of irony in translation by identifying stylistic differences in regional manifestations of the English language. This shows the necessity of deeply studying not only linguistic differences but also the cultural contexts behind them when translating irony.

Maslennikova's research titled "Linguistic Interpretation of Hidden Meanings" serves as a theoretical foundation for analyzing the semantic complexity of irony and its multi-layered content. The author systematically analyzes linguistic devices expressing hidden meanings and studies them in connection with pragmatic strategies in the speech process. She considers irony as one of the effective methods of creating hidden semantic layers and determines how it is formed through linguistic structures. Maslennikova's research proposes the idea that ironic expressions are based on the contradiction between surface grammatical construction and internal semantic meaning. In the translation process, identifying this very contradiction and adequately expressing it in the appropriate language is considered one of the most important tasks for the translator. The concepts of context and implicature occupy a central place in the research. Maslennikova emphasizes the necessity of considering interpretation based not only on the linguistic system but also on speech situation, social role, and cultural experience when interpreting hidden meanings.[4] This approach requires paying special attention to identifying connotative and emotional components rather than literal meaning when translating irony. Maslennikova's works show the necessity of relying on linguopragmatic criteria for understanding semantic depth in translation theory and creating it equivalently in another language. This requires interdisciplinary integration in the identification and re-expression of irony in translation activity. Maslennikova's approach enables deep and unconventional interpretation of irony's content and creates the necessary theoretical foundation for its transfer in translation based on stylistic fidelity.

Lazareva's scientific research titled "Linguistic Devices Expressing Irony Based on Norwegian Journalistic Texts" is aimed at studying what linguistic forms irony manifests in journalistic style. The author describes irony as a device that expands the expressive-aesthetic possibilities of language by analyzing its functional features. In the research, structures that generate irony within the specific grammatical and semantic system of the Norwegian language are detailed and classified. Lazareva defines the communicative function of irony in journalistic genres as a means of social criticism, satirical evaluation, and unconventional attitude toward controversial events. While analyzing the contextual dependence of irony, she substantiates that the role of linguistic devices in expressing harmony between emotional tone and semantic contradictions in the text is important. From a translation theory perspective, this research shows that the multi-faceted and polysemantic nature of irony requires syntactic transformation and stylistic adequacy to convey it with fidelity in another language.[5] Lazareva's analysis particularly emphasizes that connotative units acquire meaning by connecting to context and that ironic effect is achieved through this connection. This approach shows the necessity of finding expressions close to the original not only in terms of grammatical compatibility but also from the perspective of communicative intention and stylistic effect in the translation process. Lazareva

does not limit irony to semantic analysis but reveals the complexity of the process of perceiving it in social-cultural context. On this basis, the necessity of deeply analyzing cultural associations and stylistic connotations beyond the structural possibilities of linguistic devices when translating ironic expressions is emphasized.

Research Methodology: The research was conducted based on stylistic pragmatics and linguopragmatic approaches. Through the analytical-descriptive method, ironic expressions were analyzed semantically and stylistically. Using the comparative analysis method, translations of ironic expressions in English were compared with their equivalents in Uzbek. Contextual and cultural transformations in the translation process were studied based on practical materials. Discourse analysis and semantic-structural approaches were applied as methodological foundations. Intercultural differences create the risk of disrupting ironic meaning in translation. For example, styles such as sarcasm or deadpan humor widely spread in Anglo-American culture may not have sufficient equivalents in Uzbek. In this case, the translator uses transformational strategies based on creative approach. Through transformation, he strives not to preserve the original irony but to re-express its communicative function appropriately. In this case, functional compatibility rather than semantic fidelity gains important significance.

Intonational structure is also an important factor in conveying irony. In oral speech, tone, pause, and stress are considered the main carriers of irony. In written text, these prosodic devices are reflected through stylistic and grammatical structure. The translator expresses this tone in written text through syntactic devices, quotations, connotative lexicon, or metaphorical structure. In this process, alternative expressive units may be introduced to replace ironic intonation.

The reception of ironic expression depends on the reader's linguistic sensitivity and cultural knowledge. In some cases, there is a risk that ironic phrases may be directly accepted seriously by the reader. This situation may lead to incorrect interpretation in translation. The translator must identify such dangerous zones and maintain balance through explanatory translation or stylistic restructuring when necessary. Determining the connection between text structure and communicative task has decisive importance in this process.

Analysis and Results: The analyses showed that correct reflection of irony in translation is connected not only with selecting lexical equivalents but also with ensuring stylistic, pragmatic, and cultural compatibility. Indirect ironic expressions widely used in English are transmitted in Uzbek more through emotional or social connotations. The translator must decode irony not only through grammatical structure but also with the help of contextual signals and cultural codes. The results of comparative analysis showed that irony has different semantic layers in various language variants. Translating irony in an intertextual environment is considered an even more complex process. Many ironic phrases refer to other texts, historical events, or cultural contexts. This forces the translator to identify intertextual references and reflect them appropriately in another cultural environment. Intertextual competence should be considered as one of the important components of translator activity. A translator with this competence can transfer ironic style to another culture without disrupting contextual consistency.

Discussion: During the research, it was determined that for adequate translation of ironic content, the translator must possess a high level of cultural competence. Lexical-level similarities are often insufficient to convey the pragmatic tone of irony. Therefore, methods of functional adaptation, semantic conversion, and cultural transformation play an important role. Correctly conveying the evaluative, social, and emotional components of irony requires contextual sensitivity and intercultural perception in the translation process. The semantic nature of irony is often based on antonymic structures. This leads to its expression through paradoxical statements

and unconventional syntax. In translation, stylistic fidelity can be maintained by restoring these structures in a manner corresponding to the original. Simultaneously, restructuring these syntactic constructions according to target audience language conventions may also be required. In both cases, the translator must master the art of re-expressing author's style without disrupting it. Translation of ironic texts strengthens the translator's critical thinking ability. The process of analyzing, recognizing, and expressing irony in another language transforms the translator into a socially conscious and culturally sensitive person. This once again proves that translation is not only linguistic activity but also social-cultural activity. During his activity, the translator functions by harmonizing not only language but also context, author's position, and reader expectations. Ironic style serves as a device requiring high-level thinking and sensitivity in this process.

Conclusion: Translating ironic style is a complex and multi-faceted process that harmoniously encompasses semantic, stylistic, pragmatic, and cultural aspects. The research showed that for adequate reflection of irony in translation, it is necessary to give priority to stylistic and functional compatibility rather than literal translation. The translator must possess the ability to deeply understand context, correctly perceive cultural signals, and effectively express them in the new linguistic environment when interpreting units with ironic content. This requires evaluating translation not only as linguistic but also as cognitive and cultural studies activity.

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